

PROJECT REPORT ON DESIGN OF ECG TRANSMITTER USING AGILENT ADS

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1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

In 1996, Intellidesign Pty Ltd (then IntelliMed) was approached by a cardiologist to design an ECG Holter monitor. This original device was a two or three lead, single channel ECG device, which could continuously record for a maximum of one hour. Additionally, the device had Polar Chest Strap capabilities for the added functionality as a Heart Rate monitor. The device could operate in four different modes: 1-hour ECG Recording Mode, in which the device would record one continuous hour of near diagnostic quality ECG trace during exercise; Event Recording Mode, in which the device would record up to 60, one minute segments around a recorded event, over a period of up to 24 hours; Heart rate Recording Mode, in which the unit would have the capacity to record up to 24 hours of heart rate information; and ECG Telemetry Mode, in which the unit would transmit, via a Radio Frequency (RF) link, a real-time ECG signal to a receiver unit.

1.2 Importance of Work and Aims of Project

The American Heart Association claims that cardiovascular disease is the cause of an average of one death every 33 seconds. In Australia, one person dies every 10 minutes as a result of cardiovascular disease. With these statistics, there is an obvious need for diagnostic devices in the prevention and detection of heart disease.

The aim of the project is to design two ECG devices to aid in the detection of heart disease.

1.3 Project Outline

The purpose of this project is to design ECG transmitter using the software Agilent ADS.

1.3.1 Tasks

The following tasks need to be undertaken:

- Design the analogue circuitry for the ECG device
- Instrumental Amplifier
- Right-Leg-Drive

- Defibrillator Protection
- Low pass filtering
- High pass filtering
- Gain stage (for maximum signal)
- Analogue to Digital Conversion

Design of Wireless Link

- Transmitter design and implementation
- Receiver design and implementation

2 Background of ECG

2.1 ECGs

In order to be able to design an ECG recording device, one must have some background into the physiology of the heart (with respect to its bio potentials) and an understanding of exactly what it is an ECG is, and its function.

“The electrical activity of the heart can be recorded to monitor cardiac changes or diagnose potential cardiac problems. The principle involved is simple: body fluids are good electrical conductors. Electrical impulses generated in the heart are conducted through body fluids to the skin, where they can be detected and printed out by a sensitive machine called an electrocardiograph. This printout is called an electrocardiogram, or ECG.”

Typically, an ECG is comprised of a series of three distinguishable waves or components (known as deflection waves), each representing an important aspect of cardiac function (as can be seen in Figure 1). The first wave, known as the P wave, represents atrial depolarization, and is a result of the depolarization wave from the Sinoatrial node (SA node) through the atria. This action precedes and is the cause of atrial contraction.

The QRS complex is the result of ventricular depolarization. It is caused by the electrical activity spreading from the Atrioventricular node (AV node), through the ventricles via the Purkinje fibers, and precedes ventricle contraction. During this time, atrial repolarization is also occurring; however its occurrence is usually masked by the large QRS complex being detected.

Finally, the T wave occurs when the ventricles repolarize. Repolarization, is slower than repolarization, hence the T wave is usually wider than the P wave and the QRS complex.

“In a healthy heart, the size, duration, and timing of the deflection waves tend to be consistent. Thus, changes in the pattern or timing of the ECG may reveal a diseased or damaged heart or problems with the heart’s conduction system.”

(Figure 1): An electrocardiogram tracing (lead 1) illustrating the three normally recognizable deflection waves and the important intervals

2.1.1 Lead Configuration

To perform a clinical electrocardiograph, it is important that more than one lead (also known as a channel) be recorded in order to accurately describe the heart's electrical activity. There are two planes in which these leads may lie: the frontal plane (the plane of the body that is parallel to the ground when one is lying on one's back); and the transverse plane (the plane of the body that is parallel to the ground when one is standing erect). For a two or three channel ECG, only the leads in the frontal plane are required.

(Figure 2): Position and orientation of the three bipolar limb leads. (Leads I, II, and III)

The frontal plane of an ECG consists of three basic leads, as can be seen in figure 2. These leads are the result of the various combinations of pairs of electrodes located on the right arm (RA), the left arm (LA) and the left leg (LL) of the patient. The resulting leads are: lead I, LA to RA; lead II, LL to RA; and lead III, LL to LA. Very often an electrode is also placed on the right leg (RL) and grounded or connected to a Driven-Right-Leg circuit.

2.1.2 ECG Parameters

The hardware of an ECG monitor, in its most simple form, is a biopotential amplifier. The maximum voltage that can be acquired at the skin electrodes is 0.5 to 4 mV (Figure 3). In order to perform any analysis on this data, the signal will need to be amplified, before any signal analysis is performed.

Parameter sensor location	Voltage range	Frequency range (Hz)
Electrocardiography (ECG) Skin electrodes	0.5–4 mV	0.01–250
Electroencephalography (EEG) Scalp electrodes	5–200 μ V	DC–150
Electrogastrography (EGG) Skin–surface electrodes	10–1000 μ V	DC–1
Stomach–surface electrodes	0.5–80 mV	DC–1
Electromyography (EMG) Needle electrodes	0.1–5 mV	DC–10,000
Electrooculography (EOG) Contact electrodes	50–3500 μ V	DC–50
Electroretinography (ERG) Contact electrodes	0–900 μ V	DC–50
Nerve potentials Surface or needle electrodes	0.01–3 mV	DC–10,000

(Figure 3): Voltage and Frequency Ranges for Some Important Parameters that are measured in the Human Body

2.1.2 Exercise ECGs

“Electrocardiograms often are obtained during exercise. These are valuable diagnostic tests. As exercise intensity increases, the heart must beat faster and work harder to deliver more blood to active muscles. If the heart is diseased, an indication may show up on the electrocardiogram as the heart increases its rate of work. Exercise ECGs are also invaluable tools for research in exercise physiology because they provide a convenient method for tracking cardiac changes during acute and chronic exercise.”

2.2 Holter monitors

A Holter monitor is a small portable ECG device named after its inventor, the American biophysicist Norman Holter. The device records the electrical activity of the heart, typically over a 24-hour period, while the patient keeps a diary recording their activities and any symptoms felt. The ECG recording is then analyzed, and irregular heart activity is correlated with the patient’s record of their activities and symptoms. The Holter monitor is useful for identifying disturbances which are sporadic and which are not readily identified with the usual resting electrocardiogram test. In some instances, the patient may manually activate an “event” if they are experiencing symptoms such as palpitations, chest pain, or irregular rhythms are noticed.

2.3 Electrical Safety

For electricity to have an effect on the body, two conditions must be satisfied: an electrical potential difference must be present; and the individual must form part of the electrical circuit, permitting current to flow in a loop through the body. Assuming these conditions are met, the actual effect of the electrical current passing through the body is dependent upon the magnitude of the current and the pathway the current takes through the body.

From Ohm's Law ($V = IR$), it is evident that the magnitude of current flowing in a circuit depends on both the voltage between the connections and the electrical resistance of the various pathways through the body. Most tissue in the body contains a high percentage of water hence it is usually considered to be a fairly good conductor of electricity. The body's surface resistance also affects the amount of current that flows through the body, with contacts being made directly onto moist skin having little surface resistance and passing a considerable amount of current directly into the body.

“The danger in one's exposure to various electrical devices is not the voltage but the magnitude and pathways of electrical current that flows through body tissue and major organs. In addition, for electrically sensitive organs such as the heart, physiological effects are also dependent on the frequency and waveform of the current.”

As previously mentioned, the physiological effect of current depends on the path of current through the body. Due to the distribution of current flow being determined by the resistance of local tissue, the electrical current tends to spread out. This leads to a number of alternate pathways for current flow through the body. It is possible for an individual to come into contact with a relatively large voltage source and experience only a minor electrical shock, whilst at the same time, application of a relatively low voltage directly to the heart (e.g., during surgery or via the invasive components of certain diagnostic and therapeutic equipment) can produce ventricular fibrillation, a life threatening arrhythmia.

Whenever electrical current passes through a resistive element, some of the electrical energy is dissipated in the form of heat. If the temperature is high enough to affect the biological tissue, damage, in the form of a burn, will result. This phenomenon is almost certain to occur when the current intensity is quite high, and the pathway is limited to a relatively small area.

When a medical device (e.g., electrocardiogram or blood pressure monitor) is connected directly to a patient, there must be some sort of patient input isolation. “An isolated patient connection not only limits leakage current levels from the patient contact points to very low levels but also reduces the amount of current that can flow into the patient connection from another (defective) device. It is recommended that equipment with isolated patient leads be used whenever the device is to be in contact with the heart or with a fluid-filled catheter located within the heart or great vessels.”

Although the two devices being designed will be powered by battery (usually in this situation there would be no need for any isolation), there is a USB (Universal Synchronous Bus) connection for download capabilities. Due to USB architecture, it is difficult to use the same input receptacle for patient leads and USB cable. Since two different plugs will be used, a situation in which the patient is accidentally connected to the computer (via the USB cable) could arise. In the event of an electrical fault, the ECG hardware could see a very high voltage, and hence a high dose of current, being passed into the patient. A situation like this must be avoided at all costs, and so it is imperative that all signal lines to the patient are electrically isolated, and that any circuitry connected to these isolated lines be powered by an isolated voltage source.

2.4 Mains Interference

Power lines and electrical equipment at 240V AC generate ambient electromagnetic fields at a frequency of 50 Hz and its corresponding harmonics. By Faraday’s law, if a closed loop is placed in a time-varying magnetic field, a current is induced in the loop.

When acquiring an ECG, a differential signal, generated by the patient’s heart, appears between the electrodes placed on the patient’s limbs. This signal is that required by the cardiologist. However, a large 50 Hz (or 60 Hz [US]) common-mode signal is typically present between each electrode and the local power-system ground. This is due to very small capacitances between the patient’s body and the power line, causing the patient to be connected to the voltage line. Similar small capacitances connect the patient to ground. A differential signal of approximately 4mV should be present at the input of the ECG amplifier; however, it will be masked by a much larger 50 Hz common mode signal. Ideally the ECG amplifier should only be receptive to the differential signal.

There are several different methods of blocking the common-mode voltage. The first being to use good quality limb leads that have been twisted and insulated. Following this, the ECG amplifier should have a common-mode rejection ratio (CMRR) of at least 100dB, and finally low-pass filtering the signal below 50 Hz will cause the common mode signal to be removed.

Another method is to implement a negative feedback circuit where the common mode voltage is fed to a third electrode via a feedback amplifier to oppose the common mode signal. This method is known as right-leg-drive.

2.5 Defibrillator Protection

Defibrillators are used in many emergency situations to restart the heart, by applying a short pulse of very high voltage. When using a defibrillator, it is imperative that an ECG be connected to the patient. Whilst an ECG device circuit would usually only expect maximum input voltages of approximately 4 mV, ECG preamplifier inputs must be designed to withstand a high-voltage (greater than a kilovolt) burst from a defibrillator, which may last from 5 to 20 ms.

Many ECG devices use neon glow lamps across the input lines, which bypass the voltage, and series resistors, which serve to limit the current flow. The neon lamps are primarily a pair of electrodes mounted in a glass casing, which has been evacuated and filled with low-pressure neon gas, or a mixture of inert gases. The impedance across the electrodes is usually very high; however the impedance will suddenly drop to a very low value if the voltage across the electrodes exceeds the ionization potential of the gas. Most lamps used in medical monitors have a firing potential between 45 and 70V. When a defibrillator is used, most of the charge is bypassed to ground and the gas inside of the lamps will ionize.

2.6 Low Pass Filters

2.6.1 Basic Low Pass Filter

Two-stage RC second order low-pass filters as seen in Figure 4, are limited due to a maximum Quality factor (Q) of $\frac{1}{2}$. When $R_1=R_2$ and $C_1=C_2$, $Q=1/3$. The Quality factor approaches the maximum value of $\frac{1}{2}$ when the impedance of the second RC stage is much larger than the first. Most filters require Q s larger than $\frac{1}{2}$.

(Figure 4): Basic Second Order Low-Pass Filter.

2.6.2 Sallen-Key Filter

To attain a larger Q value, a positive feedback amplifier may be used. If the positive feedback is controlled (localized to the cut-off frequency of the filter) almost any Q can be realized. However, Q values are limited by the physical constraints of the power supply and component tolerances. In 1955, R. P. Sallen and E. L. Key described these filter circuits, and hence they are generally known as Sallen-Key filters.

The operation of a Sallen-Key filter can be described qualitatively:

- At low frequencies, the signal is buffered to the output. (C1 and C2 appear as open circuits)
- At high frequencies, the signal is shunted to ground at the amplifier's input. This causes no signal to be seen at V_o. (C1 and C2 appear as short circuits)
- Near the cut-off frequency, there is positive feedback through C2, which enhances the Q of the signal. (The impedance of C1 and C2 is of the same order as R1 and R2)

The standard frequency domain equation for a second order low-pass filter is:

$$H_{LP} = \frac{K}{-\left(\frac{f}{f_c}\right)^2 + \frac{jf}{Qf_c} + 1} \quad [2.6.2-1]$$

Where f_c is the corner frequency and Q is the quality factor. When $f \ll f_c$ Equation

[2.6.2-1] reduces to K , and the circuit passes signals multiplied by a gain factor K . When $f=f_c$, Equation [2.6.2-1] reduces to $-jKQ$, and signals are enhanced by the factor Q . When $f \gg f_c$, Equation [2.6.2-1] reduces to $-K(f_c/f)^2$ and signals are attenuated by the square of the frequency ratio, which indicates a second order low-pass filter.

Figure 5 shows the Sallen-Key circuit configured for low-pass:

(Figure 5): Low-Pass Sallen-Key Circuit

$$\text{where: } Z_1=R_1, \quad Z_2=R_2, \quad Z_3=\frac{1}{sC_1}, \quad Z_4=\frac{1}{sC_2}, \quad \text{and } K=1+\frac{R_4}{R_3}$$

The ideal low-pass Sallen-Key transfer function is:

$$\frac{V_o}{V_i}(lp) = \frac{K}{s^2(R_1R_2C_1C_2) + s(R_1C_1 + R_2C_1 + R_1C_2(1-K)) + 1}$$

$$\text{where: } s = j2\pi f, \quad f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{R_1R_2C_1C_2}}, \quad \text{and } Q = \frac{\sqrt{R_1R_2C_1C_2}}{R_1C_1 + R_2C_1 + R_1C_2(1-K)}$$

These equations can be simplified to make them more efficient.

2.6.3 Quality factor considerations:

$Q < 0.5$ the poles of the transfer function are real.

$Q > 0.5$ the poles are complex.

$Q > 0.707$ the frequency response peaks above H_0 just beyond the corner frequency.

This peak can be quite large for large Q values.

$Q = 0.707$ this Q produces a maximally flat response, i.e. the sharpest fall-off near the corner without any peaks larger than H_0 .

[H_0 = maximum gain]

2.6.4 Simplification 2: Set Filter Components Equal

When $R_1=R_2=R$, and $C_1=C_2=C$, $f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$, and $Q = \frac{1}{3-K}$.

This now means that f_c and Q are independent of one another, thus simplified greatly. The gain (K) of the circuit now determines Q . RC sets f_c , (the capacitor is chosen and the resistor calculated).

2.6.5 Component Selection

Theoretically, any values of R and C that satisfy the equations may be used, but practical considerations call for component selection guidelines to be followed. In the case of the low-pass Sallen-Key filter, the ratio between the output impedance of the amplifier and the value of filter component R sets the transfer functions seen at frequencies well above cut-off. The larger the value of R , the lower the transmission of signals at high frequency. Making R too large has consequences in that C may become so small that the parasitic capacitors, including the input capacitance of the amplifier, cause errors.

The best choice of component values depends on the particulars of your circuit and the tradeoffs you are willing to make. General recommendations are as follows:

1. *Capacitors*

- Avoid values less than 100 pF.
- Use NPO if at all possible. X7R is OK in a pinch. Avoid Z5U and other low quality dielectrics. In critical applications, even higher quality dielectrics like polyester, polycarbonate, mylar, etc., may be required.
- Use 1% tolerance components. 1%, 50V, NPO, SMD, ceramic caps in standard E12 series values are available from various sources.
- Surface mount is preferred.

2. *Resistors*

- Values in the range of 10k_Ω to 200k_Ω are best.
- Use metal film with low temperature coefficients.
- Use 1% tolerance (or better).
- Surface mount is preferred.

2.7 Telemetry

Wireless medical telemetry is generally used in the remote monitoring of a patient's physiological parameters (e.g., cardiac signals) via a radio-frequency (RF) link. The use of wireless medical telemetry allows patients greater mobility by freeing them from the need to be connected to hospital equipment that would otherwise be required to monitor their condition. Telemetry can also be used to monitor an athlete's cardiac parameters as they train.

In recent years the USA, Europe and Australia have all introduced a new unlicensed band (ISM band) for Industrial Scientific and Medical applications. Australia has reserved the 918-926 MHz band for ISM applications. The US has a similar yet wider ISM band with the frequency range from 902-928 MHz reserved. Therefore a device can be designed in Australia and be distributed in the US, with absolutely no need for alteration.

Many Transceiver integrated circuits (IC's) can be found on the market today. These devices are designed especially to operate (Transmit and Receive) within the standard ISM band.

3. Isolated ECG hardware

3.1 ECG Amplifier

In order to have a good signal to noise ratio, differential amplifiers are used. Since the output is proportional to the difference between the two voltages, this circuit has a fairly good common mode rejection. Unfortunately, the differential amplifier's performance is limited due to low input impedance. This problem has been avoided by incorporating a dual Instrumentation amplifier in place of a differential amplifier.

The instrumentation amplifier chosen (INA2321), is a micro Power, Single-Supply CMOS dual device from Texas Instruments. The INA2321 provides low-cost, low noise amplification of differential signals and boasts a micro power current consumption of just 40 μ A/channel and a high CMRR of 94 dB, and states as one of its applications the use in physiological amplifiers, in particular ECGs.

SPECIFICATIONS: $V_S = +2.7V$ TO $+5.5V$

BOLDFACE limits apply over the specified temperature range, $T_A = -55^{\circ}C$ TO $125^{\circ}C$

At $T_A = +25^{\circ}C$, $R_L = 25k\Omega$, $G = 25$, and I_A common = $V_S/2$, unless otherwise noted.

PARAMETER	CONDITION	INA321E			INA321EA INA2321EA			UNITS
		MIN	TYP	MAX	MIN	TYP	MAX	
INPUT Input Offset Voltage, RTI	$V_S = +5V$		± 0.2	± 0.5		*	1	mV
Overload Recovery	50% Input Overload $G = 25$		2			*		μs
POWER SUPPLY Specified Voltage Range		+2.7		+5.5	*		*	V
Operating Voltage Range			+2.5 to +5.5		*		*	V
Quiescent Current per Channel Over Temperature	I_Q $V_{SD} > 2.5^{(4)}$		40	60		*	*	μA
Shutdown Quiescent Current/Chan	I_{SD} $V_{SD} < 0.8^{(4)}$		0.01	1	*		*	μA
TEMPERATURE RANGE Specified Range		-55		+125	*		*	$^{\circ}C$
Operating/Storage Range		-65		+150	*		*	$^{\circ}C$
Thermal Resistance	θ_{JA} MSOP-8, TSSOP-14 Surface Mount		150			*		$^{\circ}C/W$

*Specifications same as INA321E

NOTES: (1) Does not include errors from external gain setting resistors (2) Output voltage swings are measured between the output and power-supply rails. (3) See typical performance curve "Percent Overshoot vs Load Capacitance." (4) See typical performance curve "Shutdown Voltage vs Supply Voltage." (5) Output does not swing to positive rail if gain is less than 10.

(Figure 6): Power specifications of INA2321 Instrumentation Amplifier

(Figure 7): INA321 Internal diagram and basic connections

3.1.1 Setting the Gain

The ratio of R2 to R1, or the impedance between pins 1, 5, and 6, determines the gain of the INA321. With an internally set gain of 5, the INA321 can be programmed for gains greater than 5 according to the following equation:

$$G = 5 + 5 \frac{R_2}{R_1}$$

The INA321 is designed to provide accurate gain, with gain error guaranteed to be less than 0.1%. Setting gain with matching TC resistors will minimize gain drift. Errors from external resistors will add directly to the guaranteed error, and may become dominant error sources.

A gain of 10 was chosen for this stage of the circuit, therefore, $R_1 = R_2 = 100\text{kohms}$.

3.2 Driven-Right-Leg System

A right-leg-drive system is an alternative to the grounding of a patient in many electrocardiograph devices. In these circuits, an electrode is attached to the right leg and connected to the output of an auxiliary op amp, where the common-mode voltage is sensed by two averaging resistors, inverted, amplified, and returned to the right leg. This causes negative feedback, which drives the common-mode voltage low. The body's displacement current in turn flows to the op-amp output circuit, which reduces the pickup of the ECG amplifier, and effectively grounds the patient.

The circuit also acts as an electrical safety device, by un grounding a patient when the amplifier stops driving the right leg due to the saturation of the auxiliary op amp caused by an abnormally high voltage appearing between the patient and ground. This causes the large parallel resistances, R_f and R_o , to be between the patient and ground. Although these resistances limit the current, they do not protect the patient, as a large voltage would breakdown the op-amp transistors and large currents would flow directly to ground.

(Figure 8): Schematic showing Right-Leg-Drive, Defibrillator protection, and Instrumentation amplifier

The right-leg-drive circuit can be seen in the lower section of Figure 8. It consists of a buffer (which gets its common mode input from the Instrumentation Amplifier), followed by a common Driven-Right-Leg circuit.

$$R_f = R_{31}, \quad R_o = R_{34}, \quad R_{a/2} = R_{30}, \quad R_{RL} = R_{63}, \quad V_o = V_{R35}, \quad V_{CM} = V_{in},$$

$$i_d = i_{RRL}$$

$$\frac{V_{CM}}{R_{a/2}} + \frac{V_o}{R_f} = 0$$

$$V_o = -\frac{2R_f}{R_a} V_{CM}$$

$$V_{CM} = \frac{R_{RL} i_d}{1 + 2 \frac{R_f}{R_a}}$$

Using Kirchhoff's Voltage Law, solve V_{CM} :

$$V_{CM} = R_o i_d + V_o$$

$$V_{CM} = R_o i_d + -\frac{2R_f}{R_a} V_{CM}$$

$$V_{CM} = \frac{R_o i_d}{1 + 2 \frac{R_f}{R_a}}$$

V_{CM} should be made very small. This can be done by making $R_f \gg R_a$, and $R_f = R_o$.

Typically, R_o should be quite large, (around 5Mohms).

When $R_f = 5M_$, $R_a = 25k_$, then typically $i_d = 0.2_A$. This then sets V_{CM} at 2.5mV, which is very small.

Choose real and available resistor values close to these:

$$R_f = R_o = 4.7\text{Mohms}$$

$$R_{a/2} = 10\text{kohms}$$

An unpopulated resistor R35 was added in the design for an alternative right-leg-drive circuit that was not used.

3.3 Defibrillator Protection

As discussed in chapter 2, ECG devices use neon glow lamps across the input lines, to provide defibrillator protection. These neon lamps are used to bypass large voltages. The maximum strike voltage (firing potential) of the lamps being used in the design is 90V. A 330k_ resistor is placed in series on each input line, which limits the current flow. 1206 Resistors have been used here, as they have a maximum voltage rating of 200V, and a power rating of .125W, which far exceeds the ratings of smaller resistors, which are being used for the remainder of the circuit due to size restrictions.

3.4 Filtering and Gain stage

ECGs have a frequency range from between 0.1 to 250 Hz. Due to noise at 50Hz from the power mains, the acquired signal requires low-pass filtering below 50 Hz. For these devices, the corner frequency has been selected at 34 Hz. To block any wandering DC effects, a high-pass filter with a very low cut-off frequency has also been implemented.

3.4.1 High Pass Filter Design & Calculations

To nullify any wandering DC effects, a simple RC high pass filter set to approximately 1.6Hz has been implemented on the ECG Hardware directly following the Instrumentation amplifier stage.

To calculate the filter characteristics, the High Pass filter equation can be used.

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$$

$$1.6 = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$$

$$RC = \frac{1}{2\pi \times 1.6}$$

$$RC = 0.09947... \approx 0.1$$

choose $C = 1\mu\text{F}$

$$R \approx 100k\Omega$$

3.4.2 Low Pass Filter Design & Calculations

An LT1496 quad channel op-amp from Linear Technologies has been chosen for use in the positive feedback amplifier. Two cascaded second order sallen-key filters have been used for the Low Pass filter. By cascading the filters, sharper roll-off and better attenuation is achieved.

Step 1: Calculate the gain of the filter from the ideal Quality factor.
 $f_c = 34 \text{ Hz}$. $Q=0.707$ (flat response, sharp falloff).

$$Q = \frac{1}{3 - K}$$

$$0.707 = \frac{1}{3 - K}$$

$$K = 1.5856$$

Step 2: Calculate the resistor divider circuit from the known gain.

$$K = 1 + \frac{R4}{R3}$$

$$\therefore \frac{R4}{R3} = 0.5856$$

Step 3: Choose values for R3 & R4

Choose R4 = 30kohms.

$$\frac{R4}{R3} = 0.5856$$

$$R3 \approx 51k\Omega$$

\therefore the actual Quality factor (Q) = 0.7083, and K = 1.588

Step 4: Calculate the filter requirements

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$$

$$34 = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$$

$$RC = 0.00468$$

Choose C = 47nF; R = 100k Ω .

3.4.3 Final Gain Stage

The final gain stage has been designed around a simple non-inverting amplifier circuit similar to the one seen in Figure 9.

(Figure 9): Non-inverting operational amplifier circuit

$$V_s = V_1$$

$$V_1 = \frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2} V_o$$

$$A_v = \frac{V_o}{V_1} = 1 + \frac{R_2}{R_1}$$

To calculate the final gain, the gains from all the previous stages must be calculated.

ECG expected input: 2.7 mV

Instrumentation Amplifier: 10
Low pass filter: 1.588
Maximum voltage output: 1.3V

$$\therefore 1.3V = 2.7mV \times 10 \times 2 \times 1.588 \times A_v$$

$$A_v \approx 15.16$$

$$\therefore 15.16 = 1 + \frac{R_2}{R_1}$$

$$\frac{R_2}{R_1} = 14.16$$

$$\text{so, } R_2 = 14.16 \times R_1$$

Choose $R_1 = 560\text{ohms}$; and $R_2 = 33\text{kohms}$.

3.5 A/D conversion

Instead of using the onboard Analogue to Digital (A/D) converter on the MSP430 microcontroller on the ECG device which would use up quite a lot of power, two micro power A/D converters from Linear Technology (LTC1285) were chosen for the following reasons: their typical supply current is a low 160 μ A and there is an Auto shutdown feature which typically draws only 1nA. This is an extremely useful feature to have in a micro power device. For the majority of time, the A/D converter will operate in the shutdown mode, only being turned on when a conversion is needed. This saves a great deal of power and in a situation where power needs to be minimal this is essential.

3.6 Isolation

For the isolation of signal lines, coming out of the A/D converter, very low-power opto couplers from Agilent (HCPL0730A) can be used. Each channel can be driven with an input current as low as 40 μA . These high gain couplers use a LED and an integrated high gain photo detector to provide an extremely high current transfer ratio between input and output.

4. Antennas

4.1 Antenna Analysis & Design

For RF designers developing low-power radio devices for short-range applications, antenna design has become an important issue for the total radio system design. Taking the demand for small size and low cost into account in the development of such radio modules, a small-tuned loop antenna on the same printed circuit board as the radio module is a good solution.

The definition of an electrically small loop antenna is an antenna such that the circumference is less than one-tenth of a wavelength. These antennas have field patterns similar to those of infinitesimal dipoles, null perpendicular to the plane of the loop and with its maximum along the plane of the loop.

This section describes the geometry and the electrical equivalent circuit for a rectangular loop antenna. Physical dimensions for the antenna are used to calculate the components in the antenna equivalent circuit and the antenna efficiency. The T matching method is presented in order to match the impedance of the antenna to a transmitter/receiver.

4.1.1. Loop antenna physical parameters

The loop antenna physical parameters used in the calculations are

a_1 = loop antenna width [m]

a_2 = loop antenna length [m]

b_1 = thickness of loop conductor [m]

b_2 = width of loop conductor [m]

For a loop antenna fabricated on a printed circuit board (PCB), the thickness of the loop conductor b_1 means the thickness of the copper layer on top of the substrate. In order to calculate the electrical parameters of the antenna, the rectangular loop has to be modeled as an equivalent quadratic loop, and the planar loop conductor has to be modeled as a wire conductor with an equivalent circular radius.

From the parameters above the equivalent quadratic sides of the loop are given by:

$$a = \sqrt{a_1 a_2}$$

$$a = \sqrt{24 \times 10^{-3} \times 41.5 \times 10^{-3}}$$

$$a = 0.031559 \dots m$$

$$a \approx 31.56 \text{ mm}$$

The calculated equivalent quadratic sides are used in the formulas below for the loop area A, and the inductances LA and LI.

The loop area is given by:

$$A = a^2 = 996 \text{ mm}^2 = 996 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^2$$

The equivalent electrical circular radius of the loop conductor is given by:

$$b = 0.35 \times b_1 + 0.24 \times b_2$$

$$b = 0.35 \times 35 \times 10^{-6} + 0.24 \times 1 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$b = 252.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$$

In electrostatic, the equivalent radius represents the radius of a circular wire whose capacitance is equal to that of the noncircular geometry.

Directivity of antenna:

$$D_0 = 4\pi \times \frac{U_{\max}}{P_{\text{rad}}} = \frac{3}{2}$$

U_{\max} = maximum radiation intensity

P_{rad} = real power radiated by the loop

The maximum effective aperture is calculated by:

$$A_{em} = \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi} D_0 = \frac{3\lambda^2}{8\pi}$$

$$A_{em} = \frac{3 \times (327.87 \times 10^{-3})^2}{8\pi}$$

$$A_{em} = 0.01283171651$$

$$\frac{A_{em}}{A} = \frac{0.01283}{996 \times 10^{-6}} = 12.8832... \approx 13$$

Electrically, the loop is about 13 times larger than its physical size. To be effective, a small loop must be larger electrically than its physical size.

4.1.2. Loop antenna electrical equivalent circuit

The input impedance of the loop antenna needs to be calculated in order to estimate the capacitor C_P used to resonate the antenna. Radiation resistance, loss resistance of the loop conductor and other ohmic losses has to be determined in order to estimate the antenna efficiency.

The equivalent circuit for the input impedance of a small loop when the loop is used as a transmitting antenna is shown in Figure 10.

(Figure 10): Loop Antenna Equivalent Circuit (Transmit mode)

The loop antenna input impedance Z_{in} is given by:

$$Z_{in} = (R_R + R_L + R_x) + j2\pi f_0(L_A + L_i)$$

where:

R_R = radiation resistance [Ω]

R_L = loss resistance of loop conductor [Ω]

R_x = additional ohmic losses (ESR in capacitor CP etc.) [Ω]

L_A = inductance of loop antenna [H]

L_i = inductance of loop conductor [H]

The radiation resistance is given by:

$$R_r = 31171 \times \left(\frac{Area^2}{\lambda^4} \right)$$

where

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} = \frac{3 \times 10^8}{915 \times 10^6}$$

$$\lambda \approx 0.3279m$$

c is the speed of light equal to 3×10^8 m/s

f_0 is the resonance frequency in Hz.

$f_0 = 915\text{MHz}$

$$\therefore R_r = 31171 \times \frac{(996 \times 10^{-6})^2}{(327.87 \times 10^{-3})^4}$$

$$R_r = 2.67585 \Omega$$

The loss resistance of the loop inductor is given by

$$R_L = \frac{l}{P} R_s = \frac{a_1 + a_2}{b_1 + b_2} \sqrt{\frac{f_0 \mu_0 \Pi}{\sigma}}$$

$$R_L = \frac{(41.5 + 24) \times 10^{-3}}{(35 + 1000) \times 10^{-6}} \sqrt{\frac{915 \times 10^6 \times 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \times \pi}{5.8 \times 10^7}}$$

$$R_L = 0.4994 \Omega$$

where

l = length of the metal loop conductor

P = perimeter of the cross section of the loop conductor

R_s = conductor surface resistance

μ_0 = permeability of free space ($4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m)

σ = conductivity of the conductor (5.8×10^7 S/m for copper).

The inductive reactance X_A of the loop is computed using the inductance L_A of Square loop with sides a and wire radius b :

$$L_A = 2\mu_0 \frac{a}{\Pi} \left[\left(\ln \frac{a}{b} \right) - 0.774 \right]$$

$$L_A = 2 \times 4\Pi \times 10^{-7} \times \frac{31.56 \times 10^{-3}}{\Pi} \left[\left(\ln \frac{31.56 \times 10^{-3}}{252.25 \times 10^{-6}} \right) - 0.774 \right]$$

$$L_A = 1.02386 \times 10^{-7} = 102.386 \text{ nH}$$

The reactance X_i of the loop conductor can be computed using the inductance L_i of the loop. For a single turn this can be approximated by:

$$L_i = \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 a$$

$$L_i = \frac{1}{2} \times 4\Pi \times 10^{-7} \times 31.56 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$L_i = 1.98297 \times 10^{-8} = 19.8297 \text{ nH}$$

The additional ohmic losses that is introduced mainly because of ESR (Equivalent Series Resistance) of the capacitor C_p is given by:

$$R_x = \frac{2\Pi f_0 (L_A + L_i)}{Q} - R_R - R_L$$

$$R_x = \frac{2\Pi \times 915 \times 10^6 ((102.386 + 19.8297) \times 10^{-9})}{40} - 2.676 - 0.4994$$

$$R_x = 14.39 \Omega$$

As the above expression indicates, the main determinate of the maximum quality factor (Q) of a loop antenna is the ESR (i.e. the quality factor) of the capacitor C_p . The addition of a resistor R_q in parallel with C_p can be used to control the Q-value of the antenna at the same time as reducing the input impedance of the antenna.

The capacitor C_p is used in parallel to Z_{in} to resonate the antenna. It can be shown that the parallel capacitor C_p at resonance is given by:

$$C_p = \frac{L_A + L_i}{(R_R + R_L + R_x)^2 + [2\pi f_0 (L_A + L_i)]^2}$$

$$C_p = \frac{(102.386 + 19.8297) \times 10^{-9}}{(2.676 + 0.4994 + 14.39)^2 + [2\pi \times 915 \times 10^6 (102.386 + 19.8297) \times 10^{-9}]^2}$$

$$C_p = 0.2474 \text{ pF}$$

The antenna efficiency can then be expressed as:

$$\eta = \frac{R_R}{R_R + R_L + R_x}$$

$$\eta = \frac{2.676}{2.676 + 0.4994 + 14.39}$$

$$\eta = 0.152345$$

4.1.3. Antenna impedance and Q-value with chip capacitors in the loop

The antenna impedance is dependent of both feed length and Q-value (read parallel resistor RQ). The Q-value is independent of the impedance of the antenna, which means that one chooses a Q-value and then chooses the feed length.

In order to ensure that the transmitter power radiation and receiver sensitivity are always identical, the Q-value of the antenna has to be exactly matched to the capacitors that will be used to tune the antenna to the correct resonant frequency. The Q-value of the loop can be determined from the following formula:

$$Q = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{1 + \text{tol}/100}) - 1}$$

The tol variable is the percentage tolerance of the capacitors. The equation assumes that the variation in radiated power due to capacitor variations should be lower than 3dB. If the tolerance is 4% the Q-value will be 50. If a higher Q-value is chosen, each antenna has to be tuned to keep the variation in radiated power lower than the assumed 3dB.

Capacitors with a tolerance of approximately 5% have been chosen for the antenna, hence the Q-value of the antenna must be:

$$Q = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{1 + \text{tol}/100}) - 1}$$

$$Q = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{1 + 5/100}) - 1}$$

$$Q = 40$$

4.1.4. Range calculations

Unlike optical IR systems, RF systems operations in the UHF band are not restricted to line-of-sight coverage. This is because of the diffraction and reflection of radio waves at edges and conductive surfaces as well as the capability of RF waves to penetrate dielectric materials.

The range calculation parameters are:

- transmitter output power, PRF [dBm]
- transmitter and receiver antenna efficiency,
- antenna range, R [m]
- free-space loss, L_p [dB]
- additional propagation losses other than free-space loss, L_x [dB]
- receiver sensitivity, S [dBm]

When the transmitter and receiver have a clear, unobstructed line-of-sight path between them, the free space propagation model is used to predict received signal strength.

The free-space loss factor L_p is given by:

$$L_p = \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi R} \right)^2$$

This loss factor accounts for the losses due to the spherical spreading of the energy by the antenna. From the equation it can be seen that the received power strength is dependent upon the square of the transmitter-receiver separation distance. This implies that the received power decays with distance R at a rate of 20 dB/decade.

When reflection and polarization-matched antennas are aligned for maximum directional radiation and reception, the communication range can be calculated by the following formula. PRF is the output power and S is the sensitivity of the antennas.

$$R = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi \sqrt{\frac{S}{\eta^2 P_{RF}}}}$$

This equation assumes that the two antennas are separated by a distance $R > 2D^2/\lambda$, where D is the largest dimension of either antenna. The operation range may increase due to the wave guidance which sometimes occurs along conductive surfaces. As previously mentioned, the free-space path analysis applies to line-of-sight propagation, hence the other propagation losses L_x such as signal reflection, diffraction, scattering and polarization losses will need to be considered. With the inclusion of these losses, the communication range can now be calculated:

$$R = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi \sqrt{\frac{S}{L_x \eta^2 P_{RF}}}}$$

Given the required range R, assumed losses L_x , sensitivity S and equal TX/RX antennas, the necessary output power PRF is given by:

$$P_{RF} = \frac{S}{L_x L_p \eta^2}$$

$$P_{RF} = 10dBm = 10mW \text{ [21]}$$

$$S = -104dBm = 0.03811pW \text{ [21, 22]}$$

$$R = \frac{0.3279}{4\pi \sqrt{\frac{0.03811 \times 10^{-12}}{(0.152345)^2 \times 10 \times 10^{-3}}}}$$

$$R = 2.036km$$

4.1.5. Selection of Capacitors and Resistor

The antenna is designed by placing three series capacitors in parallel with a resistor. This resistor determines the Quality factor of the circuit.

Capacitors in series:

$$C_p = \left(\frac{1}{C_1} + \frac{1}{C_2} + \frac{1}{C_3} \right)^{-1}$$

$$0.2474 \times 10^{-12} = \left(\frac{1}{C_1} + \frac{1}{C_2} + \frac{1}{C_3} \right)^{-1}$$

$$4.042 \times 10^{12} = \frac{1}{C_1} + \frac{1}{C_2} + \frac{1}{C_3}$$

$$4.042 \times 10^{12} = 3 \times \frac{1}{C_x}$$

$$4.042 \times 10^{12} = 3 \times \frac{1}{C_x}$$

$$C_x = 0.74 \text{ pF}$$

∴ choose real capacitor values in this vicinity.

$$C_1 = 0.56 \text{ pF}$$

$$C_2 = 0.82 \text{ pF}$$

$$C_3 = 1.00 \text{ pF}$$

$$C_p = \left(\frac{1}{0.56 \text{ pF}} + \frac{1}{0.82 \text{ pF}} + \frac{1}{1.00 \text{ pF}} \right)^{-1}$$

$$C_p = 0.2496 \text{ pF}$$

The manufacturer of the transceiver chip (Nordic VLSI) recommends the use of an 18kohm 1% resistor for R_q .

4.2 Wireless link hardware implementation

The Transceiver and Receiver circuits are very similar. To have a matched wireless link, the antennas need to be identical, and the Transceiver chip's external circuitry remains the same. The majority of the external components were taken directly from the nRF903 Transceiver datasheet, with the exception of the antenna components which were calculated in the Antenna design section (4.3) of this project

4.2.1. Transmitter

The Transmitter circuit begins with a rotary locking FPC connector along which the power and four output lines from the primary ECG device are input. One of the data lines serves to power up the wireless board, by switching on a P-channel MOSFET. When there is no signal, the MOSFET is off, because the data line is high at 3.3V and no current is drained across the resistor. When the line is switched to an active high, the data line will read low at 0V, and the MOSFET will turn on, thus providing power to the Transmitter circuit.

The three other data lines are used in the following way: Data line for the transmission of serial data; a Clock line to read the data in from; and a Transmit enable line which when high, tells the on-board microcontroller (MSP430F1232) to put the Transceiver chip into transmit mode, by passing along a high to the TXEN pin.

The microcontroller (MSP430F1232) is the link between the input data lines and the Transceiver chip. It initiates and configures the nRF903 and is responsible for the passing of ECG waveform data to the wireless link.

4.2.2. Receiver

As previously mentioned, the Receiver hardware is not unlike the Transmitter hardware, except for the addition of a USB circuit. Data is now input via the RF link which passes the data to the onboard microcontroller (MSP430F1232 - same model as the Transmitter microcontroller).

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5. Simulation

This application notes describes a RF transmitter system simulation using Agilent Advanced Design System (ADS). When using RFIC chipset to design a RF transmitter system, it is important to select a suitable set of chips, which match the required performance. ADS gives us a visual lab for selecting RFIC chip. In this application notes, the key steps in building the system schematic and computer simulation results using ADS are presented.

System Schematic and Parameter Setting

The smart antenna transmit system consists of one base band up-converter, one IF amplifier, two IF filters, one RF up-converter, two RF filters, one RF pre-amplifier, and one RF power amplifier. We need to make sure that the system will have enough output power, linearity and sufficient attenuation on unwanted frequency spectrum.

The entire component models can be selected from RF/Analog library. Amplifier and mixer models can be obtained from the system amplifier and mixer library. Filter models are acquired from band pass filter library. The two local oscillator models are obtained from sources in frequency domain library. P_1 tone source in harmonic balance library is selected to simulate the base band input signal. Finally, a 50 Ohm terminal in harmonic balance library is used to terminate the transmitter output.

Because all the RFIC chips have detailed specifications, the parameter settings in each corresponding model should be set up as close as what can be gotten from the specifications. In setting parameter to an amplifier, it is important to use correct parameter such as noise figure, gain, power saturation point (Psat), three order intercept (TOI) power. The gain compress characteristic parameter of amplifier is fundamental to system nonlinearity characteristic simulation. While setting parameter of a mixer, P_{lomin} should be taken care of. The meaning of P_{lomin} is the minimum Local oscillator input power before mixer starved. But for some unknown reason, it had better to leave it blank. Otherwise, an error convention gain would occur.

Filter is the only kind of component determining the system band pass characteristic; correct filter models should be selected to emulate real filter performance. In the design, all the filters selected are Butterworth type. All the

parameters of filters, such as center frequency, insertion loss, pass band width, stop bandwidth, pass band ripple, and stop band attenuation, etc., are adopted from the real filter specifications.

PLL frequency synthesizers are used as the first local oscillator and the second local oscillator for up convention, in order to achieve enough short term and long-term frequency stability. The phase noise of the two synthesizers is derived from the performance of selected reference frequency and VCO. Both of the two local sources use oscillator with phase noise in frequency domain source library to simulate. The phase noise parameter of the two models depends on the derived result.

Simulation Result

The simulation setup shown in Fig.2 is used to simulate the system performance.

Harmonic Balance simulator HB1 is used to investigate the performance of the system output spectrum. While doing the harmonic balance simulation, the base band frequency is 40MHz. The frequencies of the two local oscillators are 160MHz and 1750 MHz. The simulation result is shown in Fig. 3. Large signal S parameter simulator HB2 is also used to simulate the system band pass performance by using parameter sweep controller to control the base band frequency sweep from 20MHz to 200MHz. The system band pass performance is presented in Fig. 4. In order to find the output power performance and system saturation performance versus input base band power variation, a LSSP simulator, HB3 that incorporates a parameter sweep controller sweep2 to control the input power sweep is used. In conducting these simulations, the gain compression calculator is used to calculate gain compression. Throughout the simulation, the IF amplifier gain is set to 10dB. Fig.5 and Fig. 6 show the performance curve of the simulation. Fig.7 illustrates the power at output port in dBm versus the input base band power variation. Finally, the sweep variable parameters in sweep2 are changed to IFAGC, which is the gain of the IF amplifier. The system gains performance versus IF gain variation is presented in Fig. 8.

Conclusions

The RF system for smart antenna transmitter presented in this application notes is a typical communication up convention channel. All the components work in large signal condition. The main tasks of the system simulation are (1) to ensure the system has enough linear output power, (2) to find out the system AC

parameter limits, and (3) to tune the component parameter to keep the system in the best working status. The system simulated is an experimental transmitter, in which many practical factors are not considered, such as the fast frequency hopping and large amount user etc. More simulations, such as ACPR characteristics, PLL time domain and frequency domain responding characteristics, and inter-modulation characteristics, etc., should also be carried out in designing commercial products.

Figure.1 System Schematic

Figure.2 Simulation Tools used in ADS

Fig.3 Spectrum at Output Port

Fig.4 System Band Pass Characteristics.

Fig.5 Channel Gain vs. Base Band Signal Power Variation

Fig.6 Gain Compression vs. Base Band Signal Power Variation

Fig.7 Output Power(dBm) vs. Base Band input Power variation

Fig.8 System gain vs. IF gain variation

6. References

1. Portable ECG Logger by Jessica Lambourn
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